

Caterpillar of *Trichoplusia sp* (Lepidoptera) affects on *Azadiracta indica* or Vice-Versa: An Anomalous Behavior

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Abstract

Azadiracta indica a common tree of India is well known tree for its insecticidal property. It has most active ingredient like, azadirachtin, Salannin Nimbin and Nimbidin etc, in leaves or seeds of Neem trees. It has activity against a variety of insect pests (UBL and Rick 2010) as well as many phytochemical properties (Patil and Khan 2016). In contrast *Trichoplusia sp* (Lepidoptera) known as cabbage loopers newly emerged caterpillars are translucent white. Once feeding starts, the larva become pale green, with a thin white line running length wise down each side of the body and two white lines along the middle of the back (Mau *et. al.* 2007a). Eggs of *Trichoplusia sp* singly feed on the lower leaf surface the leaf. Eggs hatch in 3-4 days, as the larvae grown they feed on the leaf margins and during severe infestation only midribs are left (Mau *et. al.* 2007b). The cases is represented in a occur incident, scientific question from them and anticipation with scientific literature followed by conclusions.

Incident: Numbers of trees of Neem in Nandubar District of Maharashtra State (21.3756° N, 74.2428° E) were affected by huge mob of *Trichoplusia sp* Caterpillars, and started feeding of complete leave of tree on November 2014. Due to huge effects and complains of local peoples, Municipal Corporation officially allows cutting some Neem tree of city. That's leads to wrong assumptions regarding the cases that after incident affected plant will not recover and it become a superstition for the case among local people. Within two days of incident all leaves of tree has been eaten by Caterpillars. Many of the people has been cut done the tree form backyards and garden those are affected, were at some incidents experts from agriculture suggested to used insecticides sprays on affected plant (Figs a-c). A month later after this incident it was found that

those Neem tree are not cut down even after infection, now they are starting growing new leaves on them. . !!. That's make séance to think scientifically.

Fig. (a). Caterpillar of *Trichoplusia* sp dropping down from Neem tree (b). Affected *Azadiracta indica* leaves completely damaged and (c). Spraying of insecticides to affected Neem Plant

Scientific Questions: While observations of all these scenarios, many scientific questions were arise like (i). How it is possible to only Neem Plant was affected by these caterpillars why not other surrounding plants, (ii). How suddenly large in number these caterpillars are come in

existence, (iii). If it is considered that all eggs are laid on same time on leaves of Neem, but how is possible for same timing for all hatching of eggs and (iv) After complete incident not father stage of these caterpillars has been observed, and no adult were seen, why. Many questions like these are aeries which we tried to solve on the basis of field observations and relevant related literature regarding topic.

Anticipations: That complete case are may due to sudden increase in temperature for area (Lindsay 2007), which may be responsible for egg hatching at same time, it can be assumed that on all plants leaves eggs were laid down for caterpillars. At this time only eggs on *Azadiracta indica* (Neem) leaves are were protected due to host (Neem) antimicrobial activity (considering no or less eggs eaters insect) result into maximum fertility is observed hence Neem as like **bio-protector** for egg and caterpillar are formed. On other hand for non Neem plant such case are not true and hence negligible fertile eggs. Hence large mob of *Trichoplusia sp* caterpillars were observed and for them immediate food materials is green leaves of their host that is Neem. Now all caterpillars are started to feed leaves and seems to affect the tree. But as caterpillars eaten leaves of Neem azadirachtin act in insect gut, it does not kill insects-at least not immediately. Instead azadirachtin disrupts their growth and reproduction Azadirachtin is structurally similar to insect hormones called "ecdysones," which control the process of metamorphosis as the insects pass from larva to pupa to adult (Lyons *et. al.* 1996). Metamorphosis requires the careful synchrony of many hormones and other physiological changes to be successful, and azadirachtin seems to be an "ecdysone blocker" It blocks the insect's production and release of these vital hormones. Insects then will not molt (Lyons *et. al.* 1996). This of course breaks their life cycle and all caterpillars' stage was cease. Here Neem acts as a **bio-controller** for caterpillar population. That may be the most appropriate anticipations for the scenario but still a question remain that what will be the core reason for abundant eggs on the same time, yes it may be environment and temperature but how? Still need to identify.

Conclusion

The matter of facts is that there is no complete effect on Neem plant at that incident, but due to local superstition some tree has been cut down. Father after the case *Trichoplusia sp* (Lepidoptera) caterpillars and even adult not observe prove that their populations has controlled were tree of Neem start flourish new leaves. Neem shows bio-protective for eggs were bio-

controller for caterpillars of *Trichoplusia sp* an anomalous behavior. The main aim for work is to avoid this type of cases in future if occurs and to find out exact scientific reasons for anomalous behaviors in ecosystems.

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